

MARKETING OF GREEN PRODUCTS AND ITS UNDERLYING PRACTICES

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Abstract:

According to the American marketing Association green marketing is the marketing of products that are presumed to be environmentally safe. Every company has its own favorite marketing mix. Companies that develop new and improved products and services with environment inputs in mind give themselves access to new markets, increase their profit sustainability, and enjoy a competitive advantage over the companies which are not concerned for the environment. This study discusses the manufacturers green marketing practices and analyze the respondents' views about Green Marketing Practices. The researcher has selected 149 units, as samples selected through Proportionate Stratified Random sampling method. The researcher uses the interview schedule instrument to collect the data from the respondents. The main objectives of the study is consists, to know the awareness level of respondents about green marketing practices and which factor more accounted to adopt green marketing practices into their business. Therefore, to know the perception level on the green marketing practices; There are 30 statements observed by the researcher which are relevant and accounted for green marketing practices. The factor analysis technique applied for the purpose of extracting the latent factors accounted for green marketing practices. From the results of factor analysis, "business ethics" factor is high loading factor to influence the sampled respondents to adopt green marketing practices. Another thing should be noted that most of the respondents in the study very aware of green marketing and its practices. Finally the researcher offers suggestion for improvement of green marketing practices.

Key Words: Green Marketing, Green Marketing Practices, Factor Analysis, KMO-Test & Sustainable Resources

Introduction:

Green marketing has gained momentum in the context of global warming and climate change. This, in turn has forced manufacturers to incorporate the principle of green marketing. As a result of green marketing need to find out the impact of green marketing on manufacturing product and customer satisfaction way to environmental safety. As resources are limited and human wants are unlimited, resources have to be utilized economically and in an environment friendly way. The obvious assumption of green marketing is that potential manufacturers will view a product or service's "greenness" as a benefit and base their manufacturing decision accordingly. Green marketing is a tool used by many companies in various industries follows this trend. Green marketing is a phenomenon which has developed particular importance in the modern market. This concept has enabled for the re-marketing and packaging of existing products which already adhere to such guidelines. Additionally, the development of green marketing has opened the door of opportunity for companies to co-brand their products into separate line, lauding the green-friendliness of some while ignoring that of others. Such marketing techniques will be explained as a direct result of movement in the minds of the consumer market. As a result of this businesses have increased their rate of targeting consumers who are concerned about the environment. It develop and promote products and services that satisfy customers' wants and needs for quality, performance, affordable pricing and convenience without having a detrimental impact on the environment. People generally want to do the right thing, so the challenge and opportunity for the green marketer is to make it easy for people to do so. When all else is equal – quality, price, performance and availability – environmental benefit will most likely tip the balance in favor of a product. The marketing industry can 'walk the talk' and become the new corporate champions of the environment. Successful green marketers will reap the rewards of healthy profits and improved shareholder value, as well as help to make the world a better place in the future.

Review of Literature:

Based on the research conducted by Azhagaiah and Ilangovan (2006) they stated Modern concept is insufficient for sustainable development. At the same time environmental condition is deteriorating at an alarming rate, mostly due to consumption-oriented marketing. Therefore, it will require a proactive corporate marketing strategy and active government involvement to encourage green marketing. Thus simultaneously influence the corporate and industrial sector to adapt the green marketing practices into their business practices.

The authors Brahma, M. & Dande, R. (2008) pin point the empirical evidence, Green Ventures in India, is a subsidiary of New York based asset management firm Green Ventures International. The latter recently announced a \$300 million India focused fund aimed at renewable energy products and supporting trading in carbon credits. Due to the evidence of the author it induce as, developing countries are more concentrate on environment friendly project and practices.

Christian Fuentes (2011), the researcher argued the retail sector implicitly or explicitly aims to understand, improve, and develop green retailing approaches by examining and analyzing existing retail practice. This study demonstrates, offers a set of practices, products, and brands. According to these studies, green communities are, much like green identities and experiences, seen as alternatives to the main- stream and perceived as rebellious constructions that enable consumers to resist and to attain market hegemony

Nitin Joshi et al. (2011) conducted the research on Customer awareness on Environment Friendly Car (EFC). The objective of the study is to understand the awareness levels and create awareness of the EFC so that the efforts of the manufacturing the green car will be achieved. Many governments around the world have become so concerned about green automobile that they have attempted to regulate them. For marketers, environmentalism has become a criterion influencing the customer purchase behaviour. There is a need to map the customer dynamic behaviour as new green technologies need to be encouraged and adopted.

Phuah Kit Teng and Golnaz Rezai (2011), Socio economic demographic characteristics and attitudes influence the consumers' intention to purchase green foods in Malaysia. The Various models have been used to explain consumer purchasing behavior towards food. The theory of Planned Behavior is a leading framework that has been used to examine consumers' behavior. To increase the awareness and knowledge on green foods in order to satisfy consumers needs and wants.

Scott Bearse et al. (2009) according to the authors thought, Sustainability movement across retail and consumer goods sectors, and it provided senior leadership with a perspective about best practices and strategies for sustainability initiatives. Since green products generate a relatively high level of product switching—and green shoppers tend to stick with green products once they like them—companies that develop and market successful green products ahead of competitors are much better positioned to gain advantage.

Manashi Medhi, (2015). Green marketing concept is evolving at a rapid pace in India. The adoption of green marketing practices by many companies has made a remarkable impact to the environment by planning for sustainable conservation of natural resources and making our environment protected. Although the government and many private companies have been making an effort to bring about a green mindset among the people and promote green products, a lot still need to be done to make green products truly viable and workable in India. Activeness about green marketing by government, companies, customer & society as a whole should be amplified as environment should be top management priority. Moreover responsibility of environment protection should be communal driven efforts. The environment and society is looking forward for practices from the companies who have not yet implemented.

Ruhul Amin et al. (2013). Green marketing concept is making all consumers aware about their rights to get fresh products; even they are ready to pay more for reducing the adulterated food. Their demand is now Government's positive intervention. Some businesses have been quickly to accept concepts like environmental management systems and waste minimization, and have integrated environmental issues into all organizational activities. Progressive communities and civil societies are now taking several environmental campaigns, including 'Buriganga Bachao Andolon', 'Campaign against Air Pollution', and 'Campaign against Polythene' was conducted by BAPA. Some of them achieved notable success. BAPA also organized 'Sundarban Bachao Conference' and 'Environmental Health Conference'. In automobile segments are also aware to reduce the carbon monoxide from the environment by starting electric vehicles and Compressed Natural Gas (CNG) conversion procedure in two-wheeler, three-wheeler transportations which are environment – friendly in different organizations. The Polythene Act in 2001 has also taken an effective movement to make pollution free environment. Bangladesh Environmental Conservation Act was enacted in 1995. As per the Act "Environmental Clearance Certification" is required for the establishment of any new industries from the Director General of the Department of Environment. Inception of such policies has strengthened the movement of Green Marketing in Bangladesh.

Study Problem:

Green marketing is the process of developing products and services and promoting them to satisfy the customers who prefer products of good quality, performance and convenience at affordable cost, which at the same time do not have a detrimental impact on the environment. It includes a broad range of activities like product modification, changing the production process, modified advertising, change in packaging, etc., aimed at reducing the detrimental impact of products and their consumption and disposal on the environment. Companies all over the world are striving to reduce the impact of products and services on the climate and other environmental parameters. So in this scenario of global concern, business houses have taken green-marketing as a part of their strategy to promote products by employing environmental claims either about their attributes or about the systems, policies and processes of the firms that manufacture or sell them.

Clearly green marketing is part and parcel of overall business strategy; along with manipulating the traditional marketing mix (product, price, promotion and place), it requires an understanding of public policy process. On the other hand, there is growing interest among the consumers all over the world regarding protection of environment. Worldwide evidence indicates people are concerned about the environment and are changing their behavior. As a result of this, green marketing has emerged which speaks for growing market for sustainable and socially responsible products and services. The researcher has undertaken the study to know the practices of green products manufacturers in Sivakasi, Tamilnadu state.

Study Scope:

This study is mainly confined to the study on green marketing practices among the manufacturers of products in Sivakasi, Tamilnadu. The applications of green marketing strategies and practices are going to be analyzed and evaluated. This study has been undertaken from the point of in three major industries in Sivakasi namely fireworks, match works and printing press. The study also attempts to analyse satisfaction of the respondents with green marketing practices and producing green products

Objectives of the Study:

- Based on the problem identified by the researcher, the following objectives are framed.
- ✓ To analyse the awareness level of manufacturer towards green marketing practices.
- ✓ To examine the factor this is more accounted to follow green marketing practices.
- ✓ To analyse the satisfaction level of the respondents about producing the green products.
- ✓ To suggest the measures to enhance the practices of green marketing in the study area.

Methodology:

Source of Data:

The data required for the study have been collected from primary sources and secondary sources. **Primary data** are those which are collected for the first time and they are original in character. The primary data have been collected from manufacturers in Sivakasi by using interview schedule. The **Secondary data** are those which have been collected by someone for some purpose and are available for the present study. To supplement the study, secondary data have been collected from books, articles, theses, published sources and related websites.

Methods of Collection Data:

The researcher has collected the primary data by using interview schedule method. The researcher has interviewed the manufacturers of green products.

Sampling Design:

According to the records available with the associations of match works, fireworks, and printing presses, there are 87 match units, 154 fireworks units, 355 printing presses operated in Sivakasi Taluk. The researcher has selected 25% of these units i.e., 149 units as samples selected through Proportionate Stratified Random Sampling method. The following Table shows the selected sample for the study.

Table 1: Sample Units Selection

S.No	Units	Total	Percentage (%)	No. of Sample Selected
1.	Fireworks	154	25% (38.5)	38
2.	Match Works	87	25% (21.75)	22
3.	Printing Press	355	25% (88.75)	89
	Total	596	25%	149

Source: Primary Source in (Tamilnadu) Sivakasi web portal

Structural Framework:

The researcher analyse the views of the respondents about Green marketing practices. There are many variables observed by the researcher. To know the views of the respondents about Green marketing practices Likert five point scaling techniques applied (the scaling options like strongly agreed to strongly disagree each graduation score allotted for 5 to 1). To know the reliability, Cronbach's test was applied, the alpha value is 0.856, the more considerable alpha value is high than 0.7. The present works out to be more than 0.7 so the researcher feels free to move further analysis. To reduce the data, the Factor analysis has been applied by the researcher to reduce and to find which factor is accounted for following green marketing practices among the manufactures of green products. . The condition should be fulfilled before a factor analysis could be carried out in the value of Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO). The KMO value is greater than 0.5 (0.589>0.5). Therefore the given set of data fit for applying factor analysis. Further the Bartlett's test of sphericity is also significant.

Results and Discussion:

Views of the Respondents about Green Marketing Practices:

The researcher makes a study to analyze the respondents' views about Green Marketing Practices. Therefore, there are 30 statements observed by the researcher which are relevant and accounted for green marketing. The following Table 2 shows the respondents views about green marketing practice.

Table 2: Views of the Respondents about Green Marketing Practices

S.No	Particulars	SA	A	NO	DA	SDA	Total
1	Following green technology in the production process	53	63	26	7	0	149
2	Using energy saving machines for manufacturing purpose	28	78	38	5	0	149
3	Always follow green sales promotions	23	61	49	14	2	149
4	Green house gas emissions are minimized	23	55	53	18	0	149
5	Purchase the raw materials from only green suppliers	14	48	57	27	3	149
6	Familiar about the bio-degradable wastes and non biodegradable Wastes	22	51	47	24	5	149
7	Bio degradable wastes are properly sent to recyclable Industries	15	41	64	27	2	149
8	Non bio degradable wastes are minimized	14	49	50	33	3	149
9	Government and NGOS are always giving suggestion to follow	14	43	51	33	8	149
10	Green practices in their business routine	12	52	45	31	9	149
11	Solid waste reduction system is followed	13	43	42	43	8	149
12	Familiar about green product, green brand and green label	19	36	46	37	11	149
13	Regularly provided orientation on green practices to our customers	23	42	55	20	9	149
14	Proper training is given to our employees about the eco-friendly business method	20	55	32	30	12	149
15	The principles of sustainable business of reduce reuse and recycle wastes are continuously followed	20	44	48	26	11	149
16	We encourage the customers to use green package	21	36	47	31	14	149
17	Willing to invest more amount for green practices	12	45	43	33	16	149
18	High potential for green product in future	16	34	60	26	13	149
19	Giving suggestion to our neighbour companies to follow green marketing practices in their day to day operation	24	42	46	28	9	149
20	Our building is a green building (more Natural light and air filled within building)	25	44	47	23	10	149
21	Fuel saving environmental friendly vehicles are used for our purchase and supply chain(transportation)	21	40	47	25	16	149
22	Green advertisement is more powerful for our sales	18	34	56	23	18	149
23	The cost of green advertisement is low	16	33	39	41	20	149
24	Our company know most of the green suppliers	9	41	50	30	19	149
25	We are aware about eco-label	18	43	46	27	15	149
26	Recycling is important to save natural resources	27	45	36	30	11	149
27	Water resources are effectively used	26	33	47	27	16	149
28	Liquid wastes are minimised and they are properly disposed	13	48	43	32	13	149
29	Government is granting subsidy to follow green practices	19	38	56	22	14	149
30	There is no air and soil pollution in my factories	19	29	47	36	18	149

Source: Primary Data

Note: SA-Strongly Agree; A-Agree; NO-No Opinion; DA-Disagree; SDA-Strongly Disagree

It is very tedious job to interpret the above statements and also which factor is more accounted and latent for green marketing practices. Therefore, the researcher applies the Data reduction technique through SPSS. In data reduction technique, the factor analysis is universally accepted and wide use in Social science research. Factor analysis is a multivariate data reduction technique. All the variables under investigation are analysed together to extract the underlying factors. It helps in identifying underlying structure of the data. Factor analysis makes use of metric data. Before applying the factor analysis technique the researcher should consider the following conditions.

- ✓ Factor analysis exercise requires metric data. This means the data should be either interval or ratio scale in nature.
- ✓ The size of the sample respondents should be at least four to five times more than the number of variables (statements)
- ✓ The basic principle behind the application of factor analysis is that the initial set of variables should be highly correlated. If the correlation co-efficient between all the variables are small, factor analysis may not be an appropriate techniques. If the researcher proves the factor analysis is an appropriate technique

of their research to carry out Bartlett’s test of sphericity. That takes the determinant of the correlation matrix into consideration.

- ✓ Another condition which needs to be fulfilled before a factor analysis could be carried out in the value of Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) statistics which taken a value between 0 to 1. The KMO statistics compares the Magnitude of observed correlation co-efficient with the magnitude of partial correlation Co-efficient.

KMO and Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity:

In order to establish the strength of the factor analysis solution, it is essential to establish the reliability and validity of the obtained reduction. The result of KMO and Bartlett’s test are given in Table 3.

Table 3: KMO and Bartlett’s Test

KMO Measure of Sampling Adequacy		0.589
Bartlett’s test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1.336E3
	Df	435
	Sig.	.000

Source: SPSS output

It should be noted that the value of KMO statistics is greater than 0.5, indicating that factor analysis can be used for the given set of data. The present case the KMO value is greater than 0.5 (0.589>0.5). Therefore the given set of data fit for applying factor analysis. Further the Bartlett’s test of sphericity is also shows significant result. The p value is less than assumed level significance (p<0.05). It result reveals the correlation matrix is significant for given set of data.

Total Variance Explained:

The correlation co-efficient between the factor score and variables included in the analysis called factor loading in the component matrix, the researcher can compute Eigen values for each factor. The Eigen value of each factor is computed as.

$$\text{Eigen value of first factor} = (0.485^2) + (0.529^2) + (0.429^2) + \dots + (0.306^2) = 3.711$$

There are seven factors with Eigen values greater than one. The percentage of variance explained by each of the factor can be computed through Eigen values. As there are 30 variables, the total variance equals seven. Therefore the variable explained by each factor can be computed as.

Percentage of variance explained by Factor 1

$$\begin{aligned} &= \text{Eigen value of first factor} / \text{Sum total of the Eigen value} * 100 \\ &= 3.711 / 30 * 100 \\ &= 12.371 \end{aligned}$$

The other factor variance could be computed as above mentioned formula. The total variance explained by both factors = 12.371 + 10.430 + 8.086 + 6.695 + 6.225 + 5.124 + 4.979 = 53.910 per cent

Rotated Component Matrix:

In order to interpret the results, a cut-off point is decided. There is no hard and fast rule to decide the cut-off point, but generally it is taken above 0.5. Now using 0.5 is the cut-off point. Factor 6, 14, 15, 16, 18, 19 and 24 not taken to analysis because these factors are less than the cut-off point 0.5.

Table 4: Rotated Component Matrix

Factors	Component						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Ist factor named as “Business Ethics”							
Using energy saving machines for manufacturing purpose	.798	.099	-.166	.133	.223	-.050	-.106
Always follow green sales promotions	.759	-.098	.004	-.054	.017	-.071	.030
Green house gas emissions are minimized	.719	.056	.154	.049	-.101	.206	-.123
Following Green Technology in Production Process	.717	.014	-.004	.014	.177	-.092	.002
Purchase the raw materials from only green suppliers	.687	-.044	.189	-.174	-.187	.146	.127
II and IIIrd factor named as “Environmental factor”							
Government is granting subsidy to follow green practices	.049	.735	.225	-.059	.064	.002	.006

Liquid wastes are minimized and they are properly disposed	0.003	.665	-.002	.295	.041	.122	-.009
There is no air and soil pollution in my factories	-.144	.635	.103	.097	.104	.184	-.018
Fuel saving environmental friendly vehicles are used for our purchase and supply chain(transportation)	-.007	.554	-.113	-.102	.031	.058	.287
Our building is a green building (more Natural light and air filled within building)	.160	.517	.019	.112	.211	-.214	-.032
Non bio degradable wastes are minimized	.157	-.078	.697	.041	-.009	.096	-.006
Government and NGOS are always giving suggestion to follow	-.028	.101	.692	.037	.223	.031	-.142
Bio degradable wastes are properly sent to recyclable Industries	.167	-.029	.645	-.057	-.061	.105	.210
Willing to invest more amount for green practices	-.068	.117	.576	.115	.008	-.094	-.077
IVth factor named as Awareness Factor							
Recycling is important to save natural resources	-.049	.229	.033	.743	.078	-.172	.021
Water resources are effectively used	-.076	.399	-.026	.635	-.066	-.035	-.010
We are aware about eco-label	-.007	-.255	.273	.620	-.168	.037	.151
Vth factor named as Business continuity factor							
Solid waste reduction system is followed	-.012	.139	-.059	-.024	.657	.110	.167
Green practices in their business routine	.081	.058	.238	-.008	.656	.126	-.012
VIth and VIIth factor named as Cost and Customer factor							
The cost of green advertisement is low	.006	-.183	.306	-.031	.129	.715	.038
Green advertisement is more powerful for our sales	-.098	.149	-.140	-.138	.224	.637	.031
Regularly provide orientation on green practices to our customers	-.076	.127	-.077	.208	.053	.219	.740
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.							
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.							
a. Rotation converged in 9 iterations.							

Source: SPSS output

Model Summary:

The total 53.910 per cent of the variance is explained by seven factors. The first factor with Eigen value 3.711 and 12.371 per cent of variance explained by first factors. The first factor consist Green technology in production process (.717), Using energy saving machines (.798), Green sales promotion (.759), Green house emission (.719) and Purchase raw materials from green supplier (.687) these factors are highly influencing factors elected by the manufacturers of green products.

After identifying the dimensions, which is most influencing factor for green marketing practices. Further the researcher uses the factor score for applying regression analysis. While applying the regression analysis, the exacted factor scores used as independent variable and respondents satisfaction towards green marketing practices is used as dependent variable. Before executing the regression analysis, the researcher

should check the independent variable is statistically independent. In order to do this the correlation (multiple) co efficient between the seven factors should be zero or less than equal to +/- 0.3. If the value of correlation co efficient is more than +/- 0.3 it leads to falsely envisage. In the present case the co efficient value of all the implied independent factor is less than or equal to +/- 0.3. After fulfilling the above said thumb rule the researcher moved to conduct the regression analysis the regression analysis results is interpreted in two essential ways.

- ✓ Model summary it results reveals as percentage of variance in the dependent variables are explained by the Independent Variable or Instrumental Variable (I.V.)
- ✓ Standardized coefficient the regression co efficient makes as to explanation of each factors in the present model in the sense of loading and influence of the dependent variable.

The results exhibited in table 5 the r^2 value is 0.754, which means 75.4 % variance in the dependent variable are explained by the independent variable (7 factors). The coefficient value of factor 5 and factor 6 works out to be the most important factor in explaining the respondents satisfaction towards green marketing practices followed by factor 2, factor 7, factor 3, factor 4 and factor 1. Further the standardized co efficient of all the factors is statistically significant at 1% and 5% confidence level. From regression analysis the researcher recommend the firm should consider business contribution and cost and customer practices for execution of green product to the society.

Table 5: Regression Analysis

Model	Unstandardized		Beta Value	T Value
	Beta Value	S.E		
Constant	4.6	0.201	--	22.88
Factor 1	0.343	0.204	0.312*	1.68
Factor 2	0.421	0.204	0.401*	2.06
Factor 3	0.403	0.204	0.389*	1.97
Factor 4	0.376	0.204	0.351*	1.84
Factor 5	0.573	0.204	0.524**	2.80
Factor 6	0.616	0.204	0.598**	3.01
Factor 7	0.413	0.204	0.398*	2.02

**1 per cent level

*5 per cent level

Satisfaction towards Manufacturing of Green Products and Green Marketing Practices:

The researcher analyse the opinion of the respondents about satisfaction while producing green marketing products and follow-up green marketing practices. The following table 6 shows the details about satisfaction of producing green products and practices.

Table 6: Satisfaction towards manufacturing of green products

Particulars	SA	A	NO	DA	SDA	Total
We satisfied with manufacturing of green products and green marketing practices	15	36	48	31	19	149

Source: Primary Data

Table 6 vivid that out of 149, 15 respondents are strongly said they are satisfied with manufacturing of green products and green marketing practices; 36 respondents-Agreed the statement; but unfortunately 48 sampled respondents in confusing stage because they are not get good or bad views regarding green marketing practices and production of green products; Balance 50 respondents are surely said they are not satisfied with the manufacturing of green products and marketing practices.

Suggestions:

It is not an easy task to implementing green business and practices because the consumers, corporate and the government play a very important role. But there are few constraints in implementing. That is lack of consumer awareness, financial constraints, limited scientific knowledge, lack of stringent rules, competitive pressures and Poor research and Development progress. From this study the researcher offers suggestion for improving and overcoming the constraints of green business and its practices.

- ✓ First of all, the firm should believe green marketing is an opportunity that can be used to meet their corporate objectives. Because most of the firm's fail to believe the green business and its practices not met their objectives.
- ✓ The companies should provide accurate information to their customer and to create awareness about usage of green products.
- ✓ Price fixation is very critical aspects, especially in green products. So the manufacturer must consider the environmentally responsible products may be comparatively less expensive than other products.
- ✓ Communication is a key to success the company's advertisement and promotional campaign to promote their commitment with their stakeholders about environment friendly products.

- ✓ Companies market their green-friendly efforts and products, they simultaneously encourage the green initiative. This perpetuates the efforts by other companies to operate with more green responsibility and causes consumers to remain vigilant in holding companies accountable for their actions.

Conclusion:

Green marketing should not neglect the economic aspect of marketing. Marketers need to understand the implications of green marketing. If we think customers are not concerned about environmental issues or will not pay a premium for products that are more eco-responsible, think again. We must find an opportunity to enhance the product's performance and strengthen the customer's loyalty and command a higher price. Green marketing is still in infant stage, in this study area the respondents are clear vision about Green business and its practices is essential to do the business in ethical way and avoid the unhealthy competition.

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